

A STUDY ON JOB SATISFACTION OF MATHEMATICS TEACHERS IN HIGH SCHOOLS

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Abstract:

High-quality mathematics instruction is a primary element for quality education and the sustainable development of society. Some studies have highlighted the critical role of mathematics teacher's job satisfaction on their instruction. However, limited research has focused on the combinational influence of job satisfaction on mathematics teachers. This study aims to examine the mathematics teachers' job satisfaction in high school level. It improves the sense of belongingness and sense of participation which leads to increase in the productivity of the organization. Being male or female does not ensure job satisfaction. You may teacher any subject or have any number of years of experience; still job satisfaction can be less. Similarly, whether the teacher resides in urban area or rural area, does not decide his or her job satisfaction. Out of the 260 respondents, 76 taken from government schools, 88 in private schools and 96 from aided teachers were participated for the purpose of the study. Data collected was analyzed with descriptive statics using SPSS version 16. This finding hints towards the fact that job satisfaction is psychological in nature. An expectation from the job is one of the major factors which effects job satisfaction. So, teachers should be told to be aware of realistic expectations that they can keep from the teaching job. The results revealed no significant differences in mathematics teachers in job satisfaction gender, location of school, pattern of school, type of management and teaching experience in years among high school.

Key Words: Mathematics Teachers, Significance, Distributions, Job Satisfaction

Introduction:

High-quality mathematics instruction is a primary element for quality education and the sustainable development of society. The current reform movement in mathematics education has emphasized the importance of dialogic instruction. In dialogic instruction, teachers are expected to work as facilitators of student conversation and wait for students to find answers to problems using conjecture, argument and justification. Increasing studies have reported the relationships between mathematics teacher job satisfaction and stress in teaching practice. Job satisfaction plays a vital role in improving the efficiency of employees but there are some factors which affect the job efficiency such as behavior in jobs like absentees, accident etc. For success in any organization job satisfaction plays a very important role. These factors are working conditions, opportunity, and stress level, relationship between management and employee and rewards. Various theories of job satisfaction like Maslow's needs of hierarchy, Herzberg's motivation-hygiene theory, the job characteristics model and dispositional approach contributed to understand the behavior of the humans in relation with the job satisfaction. Education is the process which prepares the individual for a productive, progressive, cultured and civilized life. The teacher occupies a central petition in the educational system. The National policy on Education (1986) admitted that no education system can rise above the quality of its teachers. However there is a wide gap between policy formulation and policy implementation.

Rationale of the Study:

The present study aims to study the job satisfaction of mathematics teachers in high school level. The role of the teachers in our society is very important. The quality of education is related to the quality of the teachers. Teachers are the architect of the students' future. A teacher who is satisfied with their job can perform their work effectively and efficiently. If the teachers work under stress, they cannot be satisfied with their job and it will create a negative impact towards the job. So, it is necessary to identify the factors that influence the teachers to derive satisfaction from their work. Teachers can do wonders for transforming the student raw materials into excellent finished goods that is as complete human beings and responsible citizens. Additional energy can be developed when the teachers are satisfied with their job.

Significance of the Study:

It is equally essential to mention that the stage of education caters to mathematics teaching troubled with many problems. For most, it is a terminal stage of formal learning. High school teachers thus have to work

hard to prepare young students for future uncertainties. To address these numerous problems of teaching mathematics and provide counseling and enriching learning experience, we require balanced and satisfied teachers with their profession. Since teachers profoundly influence learners, studies focusing on teachers and their numerous problems can be justified. Therefore, dwelling upon the inconsistencies found in previous studies, the investigator attempted to understand the phenomena of job satisfaction of mathematics teachers mainly of high school level. Thus, the study would accrue benefits to stakeholders in chalking out the truly deserved reforms.

Research Design:

The present study is a descriptive research. The main aim of this study to find the job satisfaction of mathematics teachers in high school level. To execute the same, results of primary data is used. A standard questionnaire has been used to collect the data. The questionnaire was designed on 5 point likert scale ranging from strongly agree, Agree, undecided, Disagree, and strongly disagree. First part was related to the demographic profile of respondents and second part contained study of factors associated with job satisfaction.

Sample Design:

In this study, the sampling unit was the job satisfaction of mathematics teachers in high school level. The sample size was selected to represent the whole population and also to give the real picture. The total size of the sample was 260. The samples were collected using Random sampling technique. Out of the 260 samples, 76 were taken from government schools, in private 88 and aided 96 mathematics teachers working in high school level were taken as sample of study.

Objectives of the Study:

To find out, if there is any significant difference in job satisfaction of mathematics teachers in high school belonging to following sub samples

- Gender : Male / Female
- Location of School : Rural / Urban
- Pattern of School : Boys / Girls / Both
- Type of management : Government / Aided / Private
- Teaching Experience (Years) : Below 10/ 11 -20/ Above 21

Hypotheses of the Study:

There is no significant difference in job satisfaction of mathematics teachers in high school belonging to following sub samples

- Gender : Male / Female
- Location of School : Rural / Urban
- Pattern of School : Boys / Girls / Both
- Type of management : Government / Aided / Private
- Teaching Experience (Years) : Below 10/ 11 -20/ Above 21

Tools Used for the Present Study:

Job Satisfaction by Dr. Brayfield and Rothe (1951)

Description of the Tool Used In the Present Study:

In the present study the scale prepared by Dr. Brayfield and Rothe (1951) was used. The reliability and the validity of this scale were high and so the researcher felt that it would satisfactorily measure the job involvement of MSFL employee's. There were 18questions. The respondent was required to answer the question in following options: Strongly agree, Agree, undecided, Disagree, and strongly disagree. Thus a respondent can obtain minimum 18 (18*1) score and maximum 90 (18*5) score. The interpretation of the scale was done on the basis of marks obtained; if the marks were high the level of Job Satisfaction was high while lower marks represent low satisfaction level.

Differential Analysis - Job Satisfaction of Mathematics Teachers in High Schools:

Table 1: Mean, Standard Deviation and "t" Values of Gender towards Job Satisfaction of Mathematics Teachers in High School

Gender	N	Mean	SD	"t" Value	Significant at 0.05 level
Male	166	65.00	9.456	0.438	NS
Female	134	67.00	9.687		

In order to find out the significant mean difference between male and female job satisfaction of mathematics teachers in high school score, the investigator calculated 't' value. It is given in the table no 1 it is found to be 0.438, which is not significant at 0.05 levels. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that male and female mathematics teachers in high school do not differ significantly in their job satisfaction.

Table 2: Mean, Standard Deviation and “t” Values of Location of School towards Job Satisfaction of Mathematics Teachers in High School

Location of School	N	Mean	SD	“t” Value	Significant at 0.05 level
Rural	148	66.00	9.123	0.724	NS
Urban	152	65.50	9.957		

In order to find out the significant mean difference between rural and urban job satisfaction of mathematics teachers in high school score, the investigator calculated ‘t’ value. It is given in the table no 2, it is found to be 0.724, which is not significant at 0.05 levels. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that rural and urban mathematics teachers in high school do not differ significantly in their job satisfaction.

Table 3: “F” Values of Scores of Pattern of School towards Job Satisfaction of Mathematics Teachers in High Schools

Group	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	‘F’ Value	LS
Between Groups	93.248	2	46.624	0.510	NS
Within Groups	27161.672	297	91.453		
Total	27254.920	299			

In order to find out the significant mean difference among boys, girls and both pattern of school job satisfaction of mathematics teachers in high school score, the investigator calculated ‘F’ value. It is given in the table no 3, it is found to be 0.013, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that boys, girls and both pattern of school mathematics teachers in high school do not differ significantly in their job satisfaction.

Table 4: “F” Values of Scores of Type of Management towards Job Satisfaction of Mathematics Teachers in High School

Group	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	‘F’ Value	LS
Between Groups	93.248	2	46.624	0.510	NS
Within Groups	27161.672	297	91.453		
Total	27254.920	299			

In order to find out the significant mean difference among Govt, Private and Aided type of management of mathematics teachers in high school in their job satisfaction score, the investigator calculated ‘F’ value. It is given in the table no 4, it is found to be 0.510, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that Govt, Private and Aided type of management of mathematics teachers in high school do not differ significantly in their job satisfaction.

Table 5: “F” Values of Scores of Teaching Experience towards Job Satisfaction of Mathematics Teachers in High School

Group	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	‘F’ Value	LS
Between Groups	1422.903	2	711.451	8.180	NS
Within Groups	25832.017	297	86.976		
Total	27254.920	299			

In order to find out the significant mean difference among below 10, 11-20 and above 21 teaching experience of mathematics teachers in high school in their job satisfaction score, the investigator calculated ‘F’ value. It is given in the table no 5, it is found to be 8.180, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that below 10, 11-20 and above 21 teaching experience of mathematics teachers in high school do not differ significantly in their job satisfaction.

Findings of the Study:

- It is inferred that male and female mathematics teachers in high school do not differ significantly in their job satisfaction.
- It is inferred that rural and urban mathematics teachers in high school do not differ significantly in their job satisfaction.
- It is inferred that boys, girls and both pattern mathematics teachers in high school do not differ significantly in their job satisfaction.
- It is inferred that Govt, Private and Aided pattern mathematics teachers in high school do not differ significantly in their job satisfaction.

- It is inferred that below 10, 11-20 and above 21 teaching experience mathematics teachers in high school do not differ significantly in their job satisfaction.

Conclusion:

Teachers are mainly recognized to play a key role in the educational process, they need to be satisfied with their teaching job, and otherwise the efforts of policy makers will fail. Teachers, who are satisfied with their job, firmly contribute towards the effective program of education. Several factors are affecting the job satisfaction of school teachers. mathematics teachers in job satisfaction gender, location of school, pattern of school, type of management and teaching experience in years among high school. Job type is an another factor which leads to dissatisfaction among the teachers like if we talk about govt teachers their salary is too high so that they can afford to met their needs while as private school teachers are undoubtedly dissatisfied because of their low wages, their requirements are not satisfied so it is clear that they are unsatisfied with their job. To sum up, the teachers truly need to be satisfied with their work in order to function efficiently and effectively. By doing so, the schools can achieve their goals and missions and can contribute in the success of nation.

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